

Lebanon Did Not Suffer Backsliding: It was Left Behind

Rita Stephan¹

Rita Stephan is a Visiting Researcher at the Khayrallah Center for Lebanese Diaspora Studies, North Carolina State University. She is the editor of *COVID and Gender in the Middle East* (University of Texas Press 2023) and the co-editor of *Women Rising: In and Beyond the Arab Spring* (NYU Press 2020). Email: rita.stephan@gmail.com.

As world values progress, Lebanese laws and politics continue to oppress women intentionally. A country governed by the consensus of sectarianism, corruption, and nepotism, Lebanon is bifurcated between repression and progress. Its former status at the forefront of progress in the Middle East in civic rights is backsliding. Its abysmal record of women's political rights is slightly improving, but social rights are nonexistent. Economic and intellectual rights have deteriorated with the financial crisis, the exodus of intellectuals, and the fatigue of the international community.

Since its independence, Lebanon enjoyed freedom of speech, religion, assembly, and expression. Lebanese journalism, fashion, and literary contributions are recognized regionally and globally (About Habib et al. 2024). Backlash in civic rights was marked in May 2023 when a woman was harassed at a public beach for wearing a one-piece swimsuit (Jamal 2023). Though the incident sparked a protest for women's right to wear what they want in public spaces, counter-demonstrations, and online backlash reminded everyone that civic rights have become subject to rising conservative norms.

Social rights are still absent in Lebanon. Resistant to change, the "Sextarian" system (Mikdashy 2022) is designed to deprive women of their right to divorce, inherit, and pass citizenship to, or have custody of, their children (Brady 2020). Child marriage, domestic violence, and exploitation of agricultural and migrant workers are still pervasive problems despite the recent passage of a domestic violence law (though without an implementation mechanism) (El-Husseini 2023; El Rahi and Antar 2023). In a nutshell, Lebanon harms rather than protects its women, and that reality has not changed.

The ongoing financial and economic crises magnified the country's pre-existing vulnerabilities. Today, Lebanon ranks 142 out of 143 countries on the happiness index (Country Economy 2024), 23/179 most fragile (Fund for Peace 2024), 31/180 most corrupt (Transparency International 2023), and 134/163 least peaceful (Institute for Economics and Peace 2024). Its global gender gap index rank remains unchanged at 133rd out of 146 nations (World Economic Forum 2024). The Lebanese failed state has abandoned its responsibility to govern or provide basic services, and international organizations have shifted their focus from democracy and

¹ The views expressed in this article are those of the authors and do not represent the views of, and should not be attributed to the U.S. Department of State.

human rights to stability and security.

Lebanon's changing demographics are depleting the country's social and intellectual capital who have traditionally fought for progress. Over a quarter million people left Lebanon between 2017 and 2021. Since 2022, a mass exodus of educated citizens included 40 percent of doctors and 10,000 teachers, while 40 percent of the population is considering emigrating (Saleh 2022). Women and refugees, who represent 52 percent and 25 percent of the 5.8 million Lebanese population, are marginalized from the labor force. Only 27 percent of women work, and less than half the refugees are eligible to and actually work (Gender Data Portal, IOM). The backlash in Lebanon is not a reaction to progress but an unfortunate outcome of Lebanon's economic freefall and perplexing demographic and social realities.

On a positive note, women's political representation that has always been minimal, is slightly progressing. Today, seven women serve in Parliament, two were nominated for president, and five held key ministries (Labor, Information, the Displaced, Justice, and most importantly, Defense) in the Mikati Third Cabinet. Because of changing public views, women have been able to crack the political representation ceiling and fight for elbow room. Attitudes towards gender equality in the private and public spheres are progressing more. Favorable views of men's control over the family have decreased from 46% in 2016 to 34% in 2022, and support for men as better political leaders has changed from 54% in 2007 to 36% in 2022 (Arab Barometer 2007, 2016, 2022). Moreover, gender advocacy is more inclusive of queer theory and sexual diversity. Institutions like [ABAAD](#) and [KAFA](#), the [Asfari Institute](#), and the [Arab Institute for Women](#) expose attacks on the LGBTQI com-

munity, sexual harassment, and exploitation of migrant workers.

Thought leaders who left are not looking behind. The international community has abandoned this country, which has failed on every scale. Meanwhile, women's rights are left to the mercy of sextarian powerholders and to the coopted population that is fighting for crumbs. Lebanon is simply left behind.♦

References

Abou-Habib, Lina, Carla Akil, and Marwan Issa. 2024. *Reclaiming and Decolonizing the History of the Women's Rights and Feminist Movements in Lebanon*. Lebanon: Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung. <https://library.fes.de/pdf-files/bueros/beirut/21196-20240612.pdf>.

Brady, Claire. 2020. "7 Facts About Women's Rights in Lebanon." *The Borgen Project* [blog], September 30. <https://borgenproject.org/womens-rights-in-lebanon/>.

Country Economy. 2024. "World Happiness Index - Lebanon." *Country Economy*. Accessed October 1, 2024. <https://countryeconomy.com/demography/world-happiness-index/lebanon>.

Corruption Perception Index. 2023. Transparency International. <https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2023>

El-Husseini, Rola. 2023. "The Harrowing State of Women's Rights in Lebanon." *Arab Center Washington DC*, May 1. <https://arabcenterdc.org/resource/the-harrowing-state-of-womens-rights-in-lebanon/>.

El Rahi, Nay and Fatima Antar. 2023. "5 ways Lebanon can #EmbraceEquity." *Countering Backlash* [blog], March 28. <https://counteringbacklash.org/5-ways-lebanon-can-embra-seequity/>.

Fragile States Index. 2023. *The Fund for Peace*. <https://fragilestatesindex.org/global-data/>

Fund for Peace. 2024. "Fragile States Index." *Fragile States Index*. Accessed October 1, 2024. <https://fragilestatesindex.org/>.

Gender Data Portal: Lebanon. World Bank. <https://genderdata.worldbank.org/en/economies/lebanon#:~:text=In%20Lebanon%2C%20the%20labor%20force,women%20is%20similar%20in%20Lebanon.>

Fund for Peace. 2024. "Fragile States Index." *Fragile States Index*. Accessed October 1, 2024. <https://fragilestatesindex.org/>.

Global Gender Gap Index Insight Report. 2024. World Economic Forum. https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_GGGR_2024.pdf.

Global Peace Index. 2024. Institute for Economics & Peace. <https://www.economicsandpeace.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/GPI-2024-web.pdf>

Institute for Economics and Peace. 2024. *Global Peace Index 2024*. Accessed October 1, 2024. <https://www.economicsandpeace.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/GPI-2024-web.pdf>.

International Organization for Migration (IOM): Lebanon. 2024. <https://www.iom.int/countries/lebanon>.

Jamal, Urooba. 2023. "Lebanese Feminists Protest after Woman Harassed over Swimsuit." *AlJazeera*, May 22. <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2023/5/22/lebanon-swimwear-protest>.

Mikdashy, Maya. 2022. *Sextarianism: Sovereignty, Secularism, and the State in Lebanon*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press.

Saleh, Heba. 2022. "Lebanon faces exodus of its most educated citizens." *Financial Times*, March 7. <https://www.ft.com/content/44633cbe-77e7-4c3f-a8b2-cce88b0af331>.

Third Cabinet of Najib Mikati. Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Third_Cabinet_of_Najib_Mikati

Transparency International. 2023. "Corruption Perceptions Index 2023." *Transparency.org*. Accessed October 1, 2024. <https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2023>.

World Economic Forum. 2024. *Global Gender Gap Report 2024*. Accessed October 1, 2024. https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_GGGR_2024.pdf.

World Happiness Index: Lebanon. 2024. <https://countryeconomy.com/demography/world-happiness-index/lebanon>